

LLMs Capabilities

In this section, we exemplify relevant capabilities available in the LLM tools mentioned by the interview participants during the interviews and pre-interview questionnaire. These examples are representative, not exhaustive. We use the terminology P# to associate with the participant #.

1st Round of Data Collection - Between October and November (2024)

- ChatGPT (P1-P6):
 - Features: Not requiring sign-up to use; powered by GPT-4o and GPT-4o mini, and other models;
 - Relevant release note:
 - Apr 1, 2024: Using ChatGPT without requiring to sign-up
 - May 13, 2024: Introducing GPT-4o
 - July 18, 2024: Introducing GPT-4o mini
 - Aug 8, 2024: DALL·E 3 for ChatGPT Free users
 - Reference:
<https://help.openai.com/en/articles/6825453-chatgpt-release-notes>
- GitHub Copilot (P1, P2, P3)
 - Features: Chat Mode, Multi-Model Support for GitHub Copilot (<https://github.blog/news-insights/product-news/bringing-developer-choice-to-copilot>), Multi-File Editing mode (<https://github.blog/news-insights/product-news/universe-2024-previews-releases>)
- Gemini {<https://gemini.google.com>} (P1)
 - Most recent version: Gemini 1.5 Pro
 - Reference: <https://gemini.google/release-notes/>
- Llama {<https://www.llama.com>} (P2)
 - Most recent versions: Llama 3.1; Llama 3.2 (first open-source multimodal large language model)
 - Features: Extended Context Length
 - Reference:
<https://hyperright.com/meta-unveils-llama-3-2-revolutionize-edge-ai-and-vision-with-open-models/>
- Perplexity {<https://www.perplexity.ai>} (P2)
 - Features: Internal Knowledge Search (<https://tech.yahoo.com/computing/articles/perplexity-two-features-beyond-jus-t-184707766>)
- Phind {<https://www.phind.com>} (P2)

- Features: Not requiring sign-up to use; Ask mode; Code mode; Free plan
 - Reference: https://felloai.com/2024/12/phind-ai-answer-engine-everything-you-need-to-know/#Key_Features_of_Phind

2nd Round of Data Collection - Between April and June (2025)

- ChatGPT (P7, P9-13, P15, 19)
 - Most recent version: GPT-5
 - Release notes:
 - August 7, 2025: Introducing GPT-5
 - Reference: <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/6825453-chatgpt-release-notes>
- GitHub Copilot (P10-P13, P15)
 - Feature: Free plan; GitHub Copilot coding agent
 - Release notes
 - December 18, 2024: Introducing GitHub Copilot Free plan
- Claude (P9, P10, P13, P15, P17)
 - Feature: Claude code
 - Most recent versions: Claude Opus 4 and Claude Sonnet 4
 - Reference:
 - <https://www.anthropic.com/claude/opus>
 - <https://www.anthropic.com/claude/sonnet>
- Microsoft Copilot {<https://copilot.microsoft.com>} (P8, P14)
 - Feature: Integration with Microsoft apps
 - Reference: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/copilot/microsoft-365/release-notes?tabs=all#may-29-2025>
- Cursor {<https://cursor.com>} (P10, P19)
 - Feature: Deeper Autonomous Agent Capabilities
 - Reference: <https://blog.promptlayer.com/cursor-changelog-whats-coming-next-in-2026>
- Llama (P9, P10)
 - Most recent version: Llama 4
 - Reference: <https://ai.meta.com/blog/llama-4-multimodal-intelligence/>
- Gemini (P13)
 - Deep reach, Gemini in Chrome; Gemini 2.5 Pro; Gemini 2.5 Flash
 - Reference: <https://gemini.google/release-notes/>
- Perplexity (P8)

- Deep research
- Reference: <https://docs.perplexity.ai/changelog/changelog>
- Mistral {<https://mistral.ai>} (P9)
 - Most recent versions: Mistral OCR, Mistral small, Codestral Embed
 - Reference: <https://docs.mistral.ai/getting-started/models>
- H2O Danube {<https://h2o.ai/platform/danube>} (P9)
 - Tiny LLM
 - Reference: <https://venturebeat.com/ai/h2o-ai-releases-danube-a-super-tiny-llm-for-mobile-applications>

3rd Round of Data Collection - September (2025)

- Claude (P20, P21)
 - Most recent version: Claude Sonnet 4.5,
 - Reference: <https://www.anthropic.com/news/claude-sonnet-4-5>
- ChatGPT (P21)
 - Features: ChatGPT Record Mode, Increased Project File Limit,
 - Reference: https://help.openai.com/en/articles/6825453-chatgpt-release-notes#h_22cae6eb9f
- GitHub Copilot (P21)
 - Features: GitHub Copilot CLI; Copilot code review
 - References:
 - <https://github.blog/changelog/2025-10-28-github-copilot-cli-use-custom-agents-and-delegate-to-copilot-coding-agent/>
 - <https://github.blog/changelog/2025-09-10-copilot-code-review-independent-repository-rule-for-automatic-reviews/>
- Jan.ai {<https://jan.ai>} (P22)
 - Feature: Improved privacy settings; support different LLMs
 - Reference: <https://www.jan.ai/changelog>
- Continue {<https://docs.continue.dev>} (P22)
 - Feature: agent mode; Documentation writing agent; Automated PR labelling; edit mode
 - Reference: <https://changelog.continue.dev/>